

Evaluation of the association constants of molecular complexes by electronic and NMR spectroscopy – First evidence for association constants measured by NMR spectroscopy being independent of the methods used

S. Muzaffar Ali Andrabi

University Science Instrumentation Centre, University of Kashmir, Srinagar-190 006,
Jammu & Kashmir, India

E-mail : smaal@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 2 September 2008, revised 28 January 2009, accepted 19 March 2009

Abstract : Modified Benesi-Hildebrand and Hanna-Ashbaugh equations have been used for the evaluation of association constants of the charge-transfer complexes by electronic spectroscopy and NMR spectroscopy, respectively. Association constants of charge-transfer complexes of aniline with various dinitrobenzenes have been calculated by electronic spectroscopy using the existing methods and compared with those calculated by the new method. Results show that the new equation has the advantages of measuring K directly rather than evaluating it from the product $K\epsilon$ leading to increased accuracy and being obeyed in cases where Foster-Hammick-Wardley and Scott equations fail. Similarly, association constant of dinitrotoluene-diphenylamine charge-transfer complex has been calculated by NMR spectroscopy using the existing and the new equations. Values of K measured by NMR spectroscopy using different methods are nearly the same, a fact not borne by other workers. This is perhaps the first report where equal values of K are obtained by different methods. The modified Hanna-Ashbaugh equation also has the advantage of measuring K directly without recourse to evaluating it from the product $K\Delta_0$.

Keywords : Charge-transfer complexes, association constants, electronic spectroscopy, NMR spectroscopy, Benesi-Hildebrand equation.

Introduction

The Benesi-Hildebrand method¹ for the evaluation of association constants of molecular complexes by electronic spectroscopy was the first and perhaps the most popular method. Due to its certain limitations several modifications of the Benesi-Hildebrand equation appeared in the literature, each claiming some superiority on the other. One of the serious limitations of the Benesi-Hildebrand equation (Briegleb² and Person³) is the difficulty in the independent determination of K and ϵ , although it is easy to determine the product $K\epsilon$. Despite some inconsistency in the values of K and ϵ evaluated by the Benesi-Hildebrand method for weak molecular complexes, the use of Benesi-Hildebrand method for the evaluation of association constants for molecular complexes widely appears in the literature till date. The Benesi-Hildebrand equation is written as :

$$\frac{[A]_0}{A} = \frac{1}{K\epsilon} \cdot \frac{1}{[D]_0} + \frac{1}{\epsilon} \quad (1)$$

where $[A]_0$ is the initial concentration of the acceptor and is kept constant throughout, $[D]_0$ is the initial concentration of the donor and is varied and always kept in large excess over the acceptor concentration, K is the association constant, ϵ is the molar absorptivity and A is the absorbance of the complex at a particular wavelength. A plot of $[A]_0/A$ vs $1/[D]_0$ is linear with the intercept equal to $1/\epsilon$ and the slope equal to $1/K\epsilon$.

Some of the modifications of the Benesi-Hildebrand method which proved useful are Foster-Hammick-Wardley equation⁴ and Scott equation⁵. Foster-Hammick-Wardley equation is given by :

$$\frac{A}{[D]_0} = -KA + K\epsilon[A]_0 \quad (2)$$

A plot of $A/[D]_0$ vs A gives a straight line with the negative slope giving K directly. The restrictive condition $[D]_0 \gg [A]_0$ is assumed. However, the equation by Foster-Hammick-Wardley seems to be applicable only when the concentration of the donor is far too large as compared to

the acceptor. This is rather a severe restriction, as on many occasions it is difficult to fulfill due to a variety of reasons e.g. solubility etc. An inherent advantage of Foster-Hammick-Wardley's method is that K can be obtained directly without recourse to evaluating it from the product $K\epsilon$. At the same time it is usually not easy to obtain ϵ by this method.

Scott equation takes the form :

$$\frac{[D]_0[A]_0}{A} = \frac{[D]_0}{\epsilon} + \frac{1}{K\epsilon} \quad (3)$$

A plot of $[D]_0[A]_0/A$ vs $[D]_0$ is linear. Here the slope is $1/\epsilon$ and the intercept is $1/K\epsilon$. The method of Scott also requires too high a difference between donor and acceptor concentration and here too the product $K\epsilon$ is obtained from the plot rather than K alone.

Another modification of the Benesi-Hildebrand equation is the Rose-Drago equation⁶ :

$$\frac{1}{K} = \frac{[A]_0[D]_0(\epsilon - \epsilon_A)}{A - A_A} - [A]_0 - [D]_0 + \frac{A - A_A}{\epsilon - \epsilon_A} \quad (4)$$

where ϵ_A is the molar absorptivity of the acceptor, A_A is the absorbance of the initial concentration of the acceptor and A corresponds to the total absorbance at any given wavelength. The method relies on randomly selecting a set of values of ϵ and calculating $1/K$ from one set of experimental data i.e. with one particular value of initial concentration of donor and acceptor. By plotting a graph of ϵ versus $1/K$ a linear curve is obtained. When the procedure is repeated for a number of varying initial concentrations of the donor and acceptor and plotting on the same graph, all these curves intersect at a single point which defines the correct value of K and ϵ . However, selecting a set of values of ϵ and applying it to varying concentrations of the donor and acceptor make the method not only laborious but sometimes difficult to apply. Moreover, in many cases the Rose-Drago plots show either an imprecise point of intersection⁷ or no intersection⁸ at all. However, an alternative graphical method of solving the Rose-Drago equation was developed by Mukherjee *et al.*⁸. The method is based on the transformation of the Rose-Drago equation into one involving three variables and using two linear plots. The authors have shown that the values of equilibrium constants calculated with this procedure were in excellent agreement with those computed by the well known iterative procedure as followed by Arnaud and Bonnier⁹ and also in good agreement with those calculated by the Benesi-Hildebrand or some other

modified methods.

More recently Pushkin-Varshney-Kamoonpuri¹⁰ equation was proposed to determine the association constants of sparingly soluble compounds. It takes the form :

$$\frac{1}{A} = \frac{1}{K\epsilon[A]_0} \cdot \frac{1}{[D]_0} + \frac{1}{[A]_0\epsilon} \quad (5)$$

A plot of $1/A$ vs $1/[D]_0$ gives a straight line with the intercept equal to $1/[A]_0\epsilon$ and the slope equal to $1/[A]_0K\epsilon$. By dividing intercept with slope we can get K . The method does not require the intercept concentration $[A]_0$ to be known. Here too it is required to evaluate K from the product $K\epsilon$. Moreover, it is not possible to evaluate ϵ by this method.

All these methods are based on a combination of the Beer-Lambert law and the law of mass action and involve the use of an excess of one component and suffer from the same disadvantages¹¹ like inconsistency between K and ϵ , appearance of negative value of K sometimes, dependence of K on the wavelength used, dependence of K and ϵ on the relative amounts of the donor and acceptor, etc. It was suggested¹¹ that the absolute values of K and ϵ obtain spectroscopically are of interest only for comparison of complex formation in series of organic compounds with similar structures and that all measurements should as far as possible be made under identical conditions. Recently Sarova and Berberan-Santo¹² also reviewed the methods of calculation of the association constant of molecular complexes by electronic absorption spectroscopy. They suggest that these equations should preferably be used only for obtaining initial estimates of K and ϵ and then final values calculated by nonlinear fit using computer programmes involving the well-known criterion (Person³), according to which the range of useful donor concentration is $0.1/K < [D]_0 < 9/K$, which is not always possible to fulfill due to solubility restrictions of the components etc. However, these equations are still being widely used and are extensively found in the current literature¹³⁻²⁴.

An inherent problem with most of these methods is that these methods lead to evaluating K from the product $K\epsilon$. According to Briegleb² and Person³, although it is easy to determine the correct value of the product $K\epsilon$, it is difficult to achieve the true values of K and ϵ from the product $K\epsilon$. This problem has been reviewed extensively²⁵. Though, this drawback of the original Benesi-Hildebrand method has been partially overcome by the Foster-Hammick-Wardley equation⁴, there is a need of a method

that conserves the simplicity of the Benesi-Hildebrand method and yet can evaluate K independently (without recourse to evaluating it from the product $K\epsilon$) and ϵ reliably. For this reason some workers^{14,20,22} prefer to report K and ϵ values calculated by more than one of these methods which is laborious and cumbersome.

In the present study a rearranged form of Benesi-Hildebrand equation has been used to calculate association constant K and molar absorptivity ϵ . It has been found successful for these objectives and also gives acceptable results even in those cases where Foster-Hammick-Wardley and Scott equations fail. NMR analogue of this equation has also been found very useful.

Experimental

The reagents used were either GR or AR reagents from E. Merck, BDH and Fluka. The nitro compounds were recrystallised till their melting points were in agreement with the reported values. Aniline was distilled thrice over zinc dust and stored in a dark bottle. The solvent used was CCl_4 from BDH. All the spectrophotometric data were obtained on Systronics-105 spectrophotometer at 400 nm. All measurements were carried out at 303 K under the condition $[D]_0 \gg [A]_0$, keeping $[A]_0$ constant and varying $[D]_0$. All the NMR spectral data were recorded on Varian 60D spectrometer working at 60 MHz.

Results and discussion

The molecular complexes of some dinitrobenzenes have been studied with aniline and were characterized as well defined charge-transfer complexes^{26,27}. In the present study other dinitrobenzenes have been studied as well.

As mentioned earlier the Benesi-Hildebrand equation leads to evaluating K and ϵ from the product $K\epsilon$. Since for the compounds in question, all the K values are rather small and ϵ values much larger, the errors in K may be formidable.

The new equation, which is a rearranged form of the Benesi-Hildebrand equation, takes the form :

$$\frac{1}{[D]_0} = \frac{[A]_0}{A} \cdot K\epsilon - K \quad (6)$$

A plot of $1/[D]_0$ vs $[A]_0/A$ is linear (Fig. 1). The negative

Fig. 1. The plot obtained by the new equation for the evaluation of the equilibrium constant of the 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid-aniline system.

intercept gives K directly and ϵ may be obtained from the slope. It is true that ϵ is obtained from the product $K\epsilon$. However, now the situation is not as difficult as in the case of Benesi-Hildebrand equation. For one, K is usually very small and hence changes in K will introduce small errors in ϵ . Moreover, since ϵ is very large, the small errors introduced will still lead to more reliable values. Table 1 gives the values of K and ϵ obtained by using the new equation for the dinitrobenzene-aniline complexes. These are compared with results obtained by other equations (Table 1). It was found that the methods of Foster-Hammick-Wardley and Scott failed for most of the complexes investigated in this study. In most cases the new equation gives lower values of K and higher values ϵ than the Benesi-Hildebrand equation. This is probably expected in light of the reasons outlined above. Moreover, ϵ values obtained by the Benesi-Hildebrand equation are often so

Table 1. Association constants and molar absorptivities of various dinitrobenzene-aniline complexes in CCl₄ obtained spectrophotometrically by using different methods at 303 K

CT complex	K (LM ⁻¹)				ε ₄₀₀		
	Benesi-Hildebrand	Foster method	Scott method	New method	Benesi-Hildebrand	Scott method	New method
3,5-Dinitrobenzoic acid-aniline	0.547	0.660	0.594	0.471	322.5	303.3	369.3
1-Fluoro-2,4-dinitrobenzene-aniline ^a	5.667	N.O	4.242	5.060	666.7	857.1	731.9
1-Chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene-aniline ^a	0.223	N.O.	N.O.	0.128	917.4	N.O.	1568.6
2,4-Dinitrotoluene-aniline	0.471	N.O.	N.O.	0.361	250.0	N.O	315.2
<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene-aniline	0.093	N.O.	N.O.	0.131	1785.7	N.O.	1335.9

Calculation of ε_λ by Foster's method has been omitted as it is rather involved.

^aSince the solvent is non polar (CCl₄), in both the cases a molecular complex is expected than a σ-complex.

N.O. = Not obeyed.

low that they may not be the true values. The new equation can be an alternative to the Benesi-Hildebrand equation and it certainly does contain the unifying features of both Foster-Hammick-Wardley and Benesi-Hildebrand equations that *K* is measured directly without the need to evaluate it from the product *Kε*, leading to increased accuracy in both *K* and ε.

Evaluation of association constants by NMR spectroscopy :

The evaluation of *K* by NMR spectroscopy is now being used extensively. The methods of evaluating *K* by NMR spectrometry use analogues of the equations used in electronic spectroscopy. The equations used are :

Hanna-Ashbaugh equation²⁸ (an analogue of the Benesi-Hildebrand equation) which takes the form :

$$\frac{1}{\Delta} = \frac{1}{K\Delta_0} \cdot \frac{1}{[D]_0} + \frac{1}{\Delta_0} \quad (7)$$

where Δ is the shift in frequency between "free" and "complexed" reactants, Δ₀ is the shift in pure complex (not measured), *K* is the association constant and [D]₀ is the initial concentration of donor, taken in large excess over the acceptor. The acceptor concentration is kept constant while the donor concentration is varied and the shifts in frequency of an acceptor peak in the complex measured with respect to the free acceptor. A plot of 1/Δ vs 1/[D]₀ gives a straight line with 1/Δ₀ as intercept and

1/*K*Δ₀ as slope, whereby *K* and Δ₀ can be evaluated.

Foster-Fyfe equation²⁹ (an analogue of the Foster-Hammick-Wardley equation). It is a rearranged form of eq. (7).

$$\frac{\Delta}{[D]_0} = -\Delta K + \Delta_0 K \quad (8)$$

A plot of Δ/[D]₀ vs Δ yields a straight line with a negative slope. The negative slope gives *K* directly.

Qureshi-Varshney-Kamoonpuri equation³⁰ (an analogue of the Scott equation) takes the form :

$$\frac{[D]_0}{\Delta} = \frac{1}{K\Delta_0} + \frac{[D]_0}{\Delta_0} \quad (9)$$

A plot of [D]₀/Δ vs [D]₀ gives a straight line with slope equal to 1/Δ₀ and the intercept equal to 1/*K*Δ₀, from where *K* and Δ₀ can be evaluated.

The new equation, which is a rearranged form of eq. (7), takes the following form (this is the NMR analogue of the new equation used in UV-Visible spectroscopy) :

$$\frac{1}{[D]_0} = K\Delta_0 \cdot \frac{1}{\Delta} - K \quad (10)$$

A plot of 1/[D]₀ vs 1/Δ gives a straight line (Fig. 2) with a negative intercept giving *K* directly. Δ₀ can be evaluated from the slope.

To study the utility of the new equation (eq. (10)), the

Fig. 2. The new plot for the 'b' proton of dinitrotoluene-diphenylamine system by the NMR method.

2,4-dinitrotoluene-diphenylamine system was selected as it has been shown to be a well defined charge-transfer complex³¹. This system has been reinvestigated here by taking a higher donor to acceptor concentration.

In the charge-transfer complex in CCl₄ there are upfield shifts of the acceptor (dinitrotoluene) protons. The maximum shift is for the proton 'a' which is under the electron

withdrawing effect of the two neighbouring nitro groups (Structure I).

Structure I

Association constants were evaluated by all the four equations taking the three protons 'b', 'c' and '-CH₃' into consideration. Association constants are given in Table 2. As expected association constants measured by NMR spectrometry vary with the nuclei being measured^{32,33}. However, values of association constants measured by different methods are almost the same, a fact not borne by other workers. Usually different methods give different values of *K*. This aspect is common to *K* measured by electronic spectroscopy^{26,27,34} as well as NMR spectrometry^{30,33}. Perhaps this is the first report where equal values of *K* are obtained by different methods. The results obtained show that the NMR analogue of the new equation proposed here satisfactorily reproduces the values of *K* obtained by other methods, showing the usefulness of the equation.

The inherent advantage of the new equation is, however, for the electronic spectroscopy viz. that *K* can be measured directly without recourse to evaluating it from the product *Ke* and gives satisfactory results even in cases where Foster-Hammick-Wardley and Scott equations are not obeyed. The first advantage also obtains for the NMR

Table 2. Association constants and proton chemical shifts for the pure complex relative to the acceptor (Δ_0) for the complex of 2,4-dinitrotoluene and diphenylamine in CCl₄ obtained by NMR spectrometry by using different methods at 303 K

Method	Nucleus considered					
	H(b)		H(c)		H(-CH ₃)	
	<i>K</i> (LM ⁻¹)	Δ_0	<i>K</i> (LM ⁻¹)	Δ_0	<i>K</i> (LM ⁻¹)	Δ_0
Hanna-Ashbaugh	0.334	59.88	0.076	95.24	0.091	142.86
Foster-Fyfe	0.333	-	0.075	-	0.087	-
Qureshi-Varshney-Kamoonpuri	0.342	59.03	0.072	100.00	0.095	118.11
New method	0.345	58.14	0.078	95.24	0.096	90.91

analogue of new equation. In addition, NMR spectroscopy seems more advantageous for the determination of K in which case the values of K seem to be independent of the method used unlike electronic absorption spectroscopy.

Acknowledgement

The author thanks Director, USIC and Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Kashmir for providing facilities.

References

- H. A. Benesi and J. H. Hildebrand, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 2703.
- G. Briegleb, "Elektronen-Donator-Acceptor-Komplexes", Springer-verlag, Berlin, 1961, p. 203.
- W. B. Person, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 167.
- R. Foster, D. Ll. Hammick and A. A. Wardly, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3817.
- R. L. Scott, *Recl. Trav. Chim. Pays-Bas Belg.*, 1956, **75**, 787.
- N. J. Rose and R. S. Drago, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 6138.
- R. S. Drago and N. J. Rose, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 6141.
- B. K. Seal, A. K. Mukherjee and D. C. Mukherjee, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1979, **52**, 2088.
- R. Arnaud and J. M. Bonnier, *J. Chim. Phys.*, 1969, **66**, 954.
- P. M. Qureshi, R. K. Varshney and S. I. M. Kamoonpuri, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 1989, **45**, 1319.
- E. G. Polle, *Russ. Chem. Rev.*, 1974, **43**, 631.
- G. Sarova and M. N. Berberan-Santo, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2004, **108**, 17261.
- P. M. Qureshi and S. M. A. Andrabi, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 1995, **51**, 733.
- A. H. Al-Taira, S. K. Shubber and A. Megherbi, *Turk. J. Chem.*, 2002, **26**, 351.
- S. M. A. Andrabi, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2002, **41**, 2310.
- S. M. A. Andrabi and S. Athar, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2002, **14**, 1077.
- D. K. Roy, A. Saha and A. K. Mukherjee, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2005, **61**, 2017.
- A. Saha and A. K. Mukherjee, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2004, **60**, 1731.
- S. Bhattacharya, M. Banerjee and A. K. Mukherjee, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2003, **59**, 3147.
- M. S. Refat, S. M. Aqeel and I. K. Grabtcher, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2004, **49**, 258.
- M. Arslan and J. Manovi, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2006, **64**, 711.
- H. Reffas, Benabdallah, A. H. Al-Taira and M. H. Youcef, *Phys. & Chem. of Liquids*, 2007, **45**, 641.
- H. Duymus and M. Arslan, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2007, **67**, 573.
- M. Arslan, J. Manovi and Krafcik, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2007, **66**, 1063.
- R. Foster, "Organic Charge-transfer Complexes", Academic Press, New York, 1969, p. 161.
- J. Landauer and H. M. McConnell, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 1221.
- B. Dale, R. Foster and D. Ll. Hammick, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 3986.
- M. W. Hanna and A. L. Ashbaugh, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 1974, **68**, 811.
- R. Foster and C. A. Fyfe, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1965, **61**, 1626.
- P. M. Qureshi, R. K. Varshney and S. I. M. Kamoonpuri, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 1989, **45**, 1626.
- M. Qureshi, S. A. Nabi, A. Mohammad and P. M. Qureshi, *J. Solid State Chem.*, 1982, **44**, 186.
- M. I. Foreman, R. Foster and D. R. Twiselton, *Chem. Commun.*, 1969, 1318.
- R. Foster, "Organic Charge-transfer Complexes", Academic Press, New York, 1969, p. 160.
- P. M. Qureshi, R. K. Varshney and S. B. Singh, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 1990, **46**, 731.